

РАҚАМЛИ ТЕХНОЛОГИЯЛАР ВОСИТАСИДА МУРОЖААТ ҚИЛИШ ҲУҚУҚИНИ ТАЪМИНЛАШНИНГ ЎЗИГА ХОС ЖИҲАТЛАРИ

Юлдашов Содик Оқбаевич

Жамоат хавфсизлиги университет профессори,

ю.ф.б.ф.д.(PhD)

Аннотация

Ушбу мақолада рақамли технологиялар, уларни қонунни қўллаш амалиётидаги аҳамияти, ахборот коммуникация-технологиялари воситасида мурожаат қилиш ҳуқуқини таъминлашнинг ўзига хос жиҳатлари таҳлил этилган.

Таянч сўзлар: рақамли технологиялар, Президент Виртуал қабулхонаси, Электрон мурожаат, Рақамли ҳукумат, видеоконференцалоқа.

ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ПРАВА ОБРАЩЕНИЯ В ПОСРЕДСТВОМ ЦИФРОВЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ

Садик Оқбаевич ЮЛДАШОВ

профессора Университет общественной

безопасности, д.ф.ю.н.(PhD)

Аннотация

В данной статье анализируются цифровые технологии, их значение в правоприменительной практике, особенности обеспечения права на обращение посредством информационно-коммуникационных технологий.

Ключевые слова: цифровые технологии, Виртуальная приемная Президента, электронное обращение, Цифровое правительство, видеоконференцсвязь.

**SPECIFIC ASPECTS OF ENSURING THE RIGHT OF ACCESS
THROUGH
DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES**

Sodik Okbaevich YULDASHEV

Associate Professor at the University of Public Safety,

PhD in Law

Abstract

This article analyzes digital technologies, their importance in the practice of law enforcement, specific aspects of ensuring the right to appeal through information and communication technologies.

Keywords: digital technologies, Presidential Virtual Reception, electronic appeal, digital government, videoconference.

Today, global digitization covers all aspects of social life. Digital economy, digital management, digital education, social networks, and similar areas are becoming commonplace in everyday life.

Since the early days of Uzbekistan's independence, significant steps have been taken to introduce digital technologies in all spheres of public administration and to cover them in the future fully.

This is confirmed by the Laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Legal Protection of Computer Programs and Databases" (1994), "On Telecommunications" (1999), "On Principles and Guarantees of Freedom of Information" (2002), "On Information" (2003), "On Electronic Document Circulation" (2004), "On Electronic Commerce" (2004), "On Electronic Payments" (2005), "On Openness of Activities of State Authorities and Management Bodies" (2014), "On Electronic Government" (2015) laws and several other legal documents.

The use of digital technologies in the field of the appeals institute serves to bring closer and strengthen the interaction between the population and state officials at all levels, to participate in society and state administration actively, and to realize human rights and freedoms in practice.

It is worth noting that the electronic appeal, which is a component of digital technologies, was first established in Article 4 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Appeals of Individuals and Legal Entities" dated December 3, 2014, as an electronic form of appeals of natural and legal entities, and it has been put into practice since that time [1; 4].

The process of globalization taking place in the world, especially the rapid development of information and communication technologies, has further expanded the content of the concept of "electronic appeal". Based on this, in Article 3 of the new version of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 11, 2017 "On Appeals of Natural and Legal Entities," it is stated that "electronic appeal - submitted by the established procedure using information and communication technologies, including posted on the official website of the state body, organization the basic concept of "address, excluding oral addresses given using information and communication technologies in real time" [1;6].

The practical use of digital technologies has created conditions for the further improvement of the scope of the appeals institute. Now, with the help of these tools, our people are aware of the reforms implemented in the country, and their results, fully aware of their rights and freedoms, use them to demand them and solve their problems, and become active in the management of society and state affairs.

Today, the Internet is a global information network, the President's Virtual Reception, "Electronic Address", "Electronic Parliament", "Digital Government" ("Electronic Government"), official electronic sites of state authorities and administrative bodies, video conference rooms, the Unified Interactive State Services Portal, " The widespread implementation of digitization technologies such

as hotlines, "Open Budget" (initiative budget), instant communication phones is an effective result of the work done in this regard.

Precisely, the virtual lobby of the Prime Minister, which was introduced on the portal of the Government of Uzbekistan on September 25, 2016, serves as a driver of significant progress in this field in recent years.

The transformation of this virtual lobby into a virtual lobby of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan from December 23, 2016, literally became the basis for a completely new mechanism of the institution of appeals of individuals and legal entities in digital technologies, which was not recorded in international law.

This is due, on the one hand, to the fact that the politics of our country is open, transparent, and transparent, on the other hand, the appeals of individuals and legal entities will be under the personal control of the head of state, on the third hand, the confidence of our people in the state power and the rule of law is increasing, and on the fourth hand, to the virtual lobby applying is very convenient and easy, modern and free of excessive formalities, on the fifth hand, the terms of consideration of applications are very short, on the sixth hand, the rate of positive resolution of the problems raised in the applications is extremely high, on the seventh hand, modern information and communication technologies are effectively implemented in our society, our people the increasing level of their use indicates that people can use the created opportunities and facilities correctly and purposefully in their daily life [2].

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on February 7, 2017 "On the Strategy of Actions for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" No. PF-4947 and the "Strategy of Actions on the Five Priority Areas of Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021" approved by this document are appeals in all areas that started a new stage of development of the institute.

In particular, in paragraph 1.2 of the Strategy of Actions, improving the "Electronic Government" system, increasing the efficiency and quality of public

services, and increasing the possibility of using this service by the population and business entities, in paragraphs 2 and 3, introducing modern forms and methods of conducting court and executive proceedings electronically. Is defined [3].

In paragraph 2.2 of the "Digital Uzbekistan - 2030" Strategy, approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 5, 2020, PF - 6079, the introduction of effective online monitoring systems ("tracking") of the status of consideration of appeals of citizens and business entities to state bodies and organizations; introducing digital technologies into the activities of state bodies and introducing a system for evaluating the effectiveness of their use; It is envisaged to further improve the mechanism of participation of citizens and entrepreneurs in the online discussion of legislative drafts, taking into account the suggestions and comments of the population, as well as increasing the share of projects implemented based on the opinion of the population [4].

According to paragraph 23 of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on January 28, 2022 "On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026", which was adopted based on the principle of "From Action Strategy to Development Strategy" as a result of a broad public discussion, Development Strategy and State Program launch of an online portal to communicate the results of local implementation to the population, in which it is determined to systematize the initiatives put forward by accepting the opinions, suggestions and objections of the population on the implementation of the measures.

Paragraph 9 of the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 21, 2022 "On measures to effectively organize the activities of the executive authorities of the Republic within the framework of the administrative reforms of the Republic of Uzbekistan" No. 447 "online reception" to identify local problems while reducing business trips to the regions, " introduction of the system of remote methods of working with regions based on modern technologies, such as

"virtual visit"[5], is a clear expression of the fact that this area has become a daily task of the government.

In recent years, the implementation of digital technologies in all areas has become one of the state's priority tasks and plans. Effective use of this technology is recognized as a human right. This right has been raised to the level of the Constitution, and in Article 33 of the new version of the Constitution, adopted on April 30, 2023, the norm "The State shall create conditions for ensuring the use of the Internet global information network" is established, which guarantees human rights, that is, freedom of speech and information. Creates a legal basis for ensuring the right to receive.

The strengthening of this norm in our Constitution, firstly, serves to improve our legislation and practice in this regard on a systematic basis, secondly, it serves to effectively exercise our rights in the online space and strengthen the security of using the Internet, and thirdly, it ensures more transparency and openness of the activities of state bodies[6; 137].

The continuous development of the Internet network by the state is a requirement of the modern world - to ensure human rights not only in the traditional form (offline) but also provides an opportunity to realize these rights in the virtual space, online. For example, conditions are being created for the provision of electronic state services, submission of appeals electronically, and other similar opportunities.

The inclusion of such a norm in the Constitution serves to improve the legislation on the Internet in the age of digital technologies, to connect the population, especially those living in remote and remote areas, to the Internet, and ultimately to ensure the right of every person to use the Internet, and the openness of society and the state[7; 67-68].

Inter-agency "Executive Discipline" on abandoning paper in data exchange and electronic document exchange with the Decision of the Head of State of May 24, 2023 "On measures to increase the scope and quality of digital services and

digital transformation of sectors, sectors and regions" PQ-162 a single electronic system was introduced and the positions of digitalization advisers of the governors of regions and Tashkent were established [8].

Full implementation of digital technologies is reflected in the long-term state programs of Uzbekistan. Therefore, in the 7th goal of the practical action plan approved by the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 11, 2023, "On measures to implement the strategy "Uzbekistan - 2030" in 2023" No. PQ-300: the new "Electronic Government" system stage — switching to the "Digital Government" system and ensuring that all documents and relations are in digital form; it is envisaged to cancel excessive formal procedures such as writing an application and filling out various forms in the application of citizens for the use of state services.

The role of the Law "On the Openness of Activities of State Power and Management Bodies" is of particular importance in the wider implementation of the constitutional rights of citizens in the field of information. This law clearly defines the procedures for informing the public about the activities of state authorities, ensuring that the population and public associations are widely informed about the decisions made by the state authorities, including the rights and freedoms of citizens, and the decisions related to their legal interests, as well as the quality of decisions. Serves to strengthen its responsibility in many ways.

The application of digital technologies through video conferencing is emerging as a widely popular tool in law enforcement today. Because video conferencing provides interactive cooperation between several distant subscribers using information and communication technologies with the possibility of real-time audio and video exchange [9].

It should be noted that digital technologies, i.e. the Internet, the global information network, the President's Virtual Reception, "Electronic Parliament", "Digital Government" ("Electronic Government"), official electronic sites of state authorities and administrative bodies, video conference rooms, "hotlines", fast It is

an effective result of cooperation between the state power and management, economic management bodies, authorities of all levels and citizens, which allows solving the most urgent problems of the population during the short period of operation of technologies such as communication phones.

On the one hand, this is a sign of the increasing confidence of our people in the state power and the rule of law, and on the other hand, the modern information and communication technologies are being effectively implemented in our society, the level of our people's use of them is increasing, and people use the opportunities and conveniences created in their daily life correctly and purposefully. Showing that he can use it.

In short, the specific aspects of ensuring the right to appeal through digital technologies are that, firstly, it provides the opportunity to use the right to appeal from home, study, work, or anywhere; secondly, it ensures getting a response about the results of the appeal in a short period; thirdly, it prevents wandering and wasting time; fourthly, money is saved materially; fifth, it prevents corruption; sixth, ensures open and transparent activities of state bodies; seventh, it puts an end to red tape in the competent bodies that consider appeals; Eighth, it increases citizens' confidence in the state.

In other words, the introduction of the Institute of appeals in digital technologies is a confirmation of the realization of the legal norm in the real sense, that "The state ensures the rights and freedoms of citizens enshrined in the Constitution and laws"[10] provided for in Article 43 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

List of used literature:

1. Ўзбекистон Республикасининг қонуни. Жисмоний ва юридик шахсларнинг музожаатлари тўғрисида. –Т.: «Адолат» нашриёти, 2015.

2. Инсон ҳуқуқлари ва эркинликлари — олий қадрият. Акмал Саидов.
[https://old.xs.uz/index.php/homepage/zhamiyat/item/8638-inson-u-u-lari-va-](https://old.xs.uz/index.php/homepage/zhamiyat/item/8638-inson-u-u-lari-va)

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3.Ўзбекистон Республикаси қонун ҳужжатлари тўплами, 2017 й., 6-сон, 70-модда.

4.Қонун ҳужжатлари маълумотлари миллий базаси, 06.10.2020 й., 06/20/6079/1349-сон.

5.Қонунчилик маълумотлари миллий базаси, 24.12.2022 й., 07/22/447/1118-сон.

6.Yangi tahrirlagi O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Konstitutsiyasi. O‘quv qo‘llanma. –Т.:«Yuridik adabiyotlar publish» нашриёти, 2024. –Б.137.

7.Янгиланаётган Конституция 100 саволга 100 жавоб. –Т.: «Адолат» нашриёти, 2023. –Б.67-68.

8.Қонунчилик маълумотлари миллий базаси, 25.05.2023 й., 07/23/162/0295-сон.

9.Ўзбекистон Республикаси қонун ҳужжатлари тўплами, 2017 й., 37-сон, 977-модда.

10.Ўзбекистон Республикасининг Конституцияси. –Тошкент: «Ўзбекистон», 2018.

Specific aspects of ensuring the right of access through digital technologies

Today, global digitization covers all aspects of social life. Digital economy, digital management, digital education, social networks, and similar areas are becoming commonplace in everyday life.

Since the early days of Uzbekistan's independence, significant steps have been taken to introduce digital technologies in all spheres of public administration and to cover them in the future fully.

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The use of digital technologies in the field of the appeals institute serves to bring closer and strengthen the interaction between the population and state officials at all levels, to participate in society and state administration actively, and to realize human rights and freedoms in practice.

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The process of globalization taking place in the world, especially the rapid development of information and communication technologies, has further expanded the content of the concept of "electronic appeal". Based on this, in Article 3 of the new version of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 11, 2017 "On Appeals of Natural and Legal Entities," it is stated that "electronic appeal - submitted in accordance with the established procedure by means of information and communication technologies, including posted on the official website of the state body, organization appeal, with the exception of oral appeals given using information and communication technologies in real time"², the basic concept is given.

The practical use of digital technologies has created conditions for the further improvement of the scope of the appeals institute. Now, with the help of these tools, our people are aware of the reforms implemented in the country, and their

¹Ўзбекистон Республикасининг қонуни. Жисмоний ва юридик шахсларнинг музожаатлари тўғрисида. –Т.: «Адолат» нашриёти, 2015. –Б.4.

²Ўзбекистон Республикасининг қонуни. Жисмоний ва юридик шахсларнинг музожаатлари тўғрисида. –Т.: «Адолат» нашриёти, 2017. –Б.6.

results, fully aware of their rights and freedoms, use them to demand them and solve their problems, and become active in the management of society and state affairs.

Today, the Internet is a global information network, the President's Virtual Reception, "Electronic Address", "Electronic Parliament", "Digital Government" ("Electronic Government"), official electronic sites of state authorities and administrative bodies, video conference rooms, the Unified Interactive State Services Portal, " The widespread implementation of digitization technologies such as hotlines, "Open Budget" (initiative budget), instant communication phones is an effective result of the work done in this regard.

Precisely, the virtual lobby of the Prime Minister, which was introduced on the portal of the Government of Uzbekistan on September 25, 2016, serves as a driver of significant progress in this field in recent years.

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This is due, on the one hand, to the fact that the politics of our country is open, transparent, and transparent, on the other hand, the appeals of individuals and legal entities will be under the personal control of the head of state, on the third hand, the confidence of our people in the state power and the rule of law is increasing, and on the fourth hand, to the virtual lobby applying is very convenient and easy, modern and free of excessive formalities, on the fifth hand, the terms of consideration of applications are very short, on the sixth hand, the rate of positive resolution of the problems raised in the applications is extremely high, on the seventh hand, modern information and communication technologies are effectively implemented in our society, our people the increasing level of their use indicates that people can use the created opportunities and facilities correctly and

purposefully in their daily life³.

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on February 7, 2017 "On the Strategy of Actions for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" No. PF-4947 and the "Strategy of Actions on the Five Priority Areas of Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021" approved by this document are appeals in all areas that started a new stage of development of the institute.

In particular, in paragraph 1.2 of the Strategy of Actions, improving the "Electronic Government" system, increasing the efficiency and quality of public services, and increasing the possibility of using this service by the population and business entities, in paragraphs 2 and 3, introducing modern forms and methods of conducting court and executive proceedings electronically⁴.

In paragraph 2.2 of the "Digital Uzbekistan - 2030" Strategy, approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 5, 2020 PF - 6079, introduction of effective online monitoring systems ("tracking") of the status of consideration of appeals of citizens and business entities to state bodies and organizations; introducing digital technologies into the activities of state bodies and introducing a system for evaluating the effectiveness of their use; Further improvement of the mechanism of participation of citizens and entrepreneurs in the online discussion of draft legislation, taking into account the suggestions and comments of the population, as well as increasing the share of projects implemented based on the opinion of the population⁵ implied.

According to paragraph 23 of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on January 28, 2022 "On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026", which was adopted based on the principle of "From Action Strategy to Development Strategy" as a result of a broad public discussion, Development Strategy and State Program launch of an online portal to

³Инсон ҳуқуқлари ва эркинликлари — олий кадрият. Акмал Саидов.

<https://old.xs.uz/index.php/homepage/zhamiyat/item/8638-inson-u-u-lari-va-erkinliklari-olij-adriyat>

⁴Ўзбекистон Республикаси қонун ҳужжатлари тўплами, 2017 й., 6-сон, 70-модда.

⁵ Қонун ҳужжатлари маълумотлари миллий базаси, 06.10.2020 й., 06/20/6079/1349-сон.

communicate the results of local implementation to the population, in which it is determined to systematize the initiatives put forward by accepting the opinions, suggestions and objections of the population on the implementation of the measures.

Paragraph 9 of the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 21, 2022 "On measures to effectively organize the activities of the executive authorities of the Republic within the framework of the administrative reforms of the Republic of Uzbekistan" No. 447 "online reception" to identify local problems while reducing business trips to the regions, " introduction of a system of using remote methods of working with areas based on modern technologies, such as "virtual visit"⁶, in fact, it is a clear manifestation of the fact that this field has become a daily task of government.

In recent years, the implementation of digital technologies in all areas has become one of the state's priority tasks and future plans. Effective use of this technology is recognized as a human right. In fact, this right has been raised to the level of the Constitution, and in Article 33 of the new version of the Constitution, adopted on April 30, 2023, the norm "The State shall create conditions for ensuring the use of the Internet global information network" is established, which guarantees human rights, that is, freedom of speech and information. creates a legal basis for ensuring the right to receive.

Enshrining this norm in our Constitution, firstly, serves to improve our legislation and practice in this regard on a systematic basis, secondly, it serves to effectively exercise our rights in the online space and strengthen the safety of using the Internet, and thirdly, it ensures more transparency and openness of the activities of state bodies⁷.

The continuous development of the Internet network by the state is a requirement of the modern world - to ensure human rights not only in the

⁶Қонунчилик маълумотлари миллий базаси, 24.12.2022 й., 07/22/447/1118-сон.

⁷Yangi tahrirlagi O'zbekiston Respublikasi Konstitutsiyasi. O'quv qo'llanma. –T.:«Yuridik adabiyotlar publish» нашриёти, 2024. –Б.137.

traditional form (offline), but also provides an opportunity to realize these rights in the virtual space, online. For example, conditions are being created for the provision of electronic state services, submission of appeals electronically, and other similar opportunities.

The inclusion of such a norm in the Constitution will serve to improve the legislation on the Internet in the age of digital technologies, to connect the population, especially those living in remote and remote areas, to the Internet, and ultimately to ensure the right of every person to use the Internet, and the openness of society and the state⁸.

Inter-agency "Executive Discipline" on abandoning paper in data exchange and electronic document exchange with the Decision of the Head of State of May 24, 2023 "On measures to increase the scope and quality of digital services and digital transformation of sectors, sectors and regions" PQ-162 a single electronic system was introduced, and the positions of digitalization advisors of regional and Tashkent mayors were established⁹.

Full implementation of digital technologies is reflected in the long-term state programs of Uzbekistan. Therefore, in the 7th goal of the practical action plan approved by the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 11, 2023, "On measures to implement the strategy "Uzbekistan - 2030" in 2023" No. PQ-300: the new "Electronic Government" system stage — switching to the "Digital Government" system and ensuring that all documents and relations are in digital form; it is envisaged to cancel excessive formal procedures such as writing an application and filling out various forms in the application of citizens for the use of state services.

The role of the Law "On the Openness of Activities of State Power and Management Bodies" is of particular importance in the wider implementation of the constitutional right of citizens in the field of information. This law clearly defines the procedures for informing the public about the activities of state

⁸Янгиланаётган Конституция 100 саволга 100 жавоб. –Т.: «Адолат» нашриёти, 2023. –Б.67-68.

⁹Қонунчилик маълумотлари миллий базаси, 25.05.2023 й., 07/23/162/0295-сон.

authorities, ensuring that the population and public associations are widely informed about the decisions made by the state authorities, including the rights and freedoms of citizens, and the decisions related to their legal interests, as well as the quality of decisions. serves to strengthen its responsibility in many ways.

The application of digital technologies through video conferencing is emerging as a widely popular tool in law enforcement today. Because video conferencing provides interactive cooperation between several remote subscribers using information and communication technologies with the ability to exchange audio and video information in real time¹⁰.

It should be noted that digital technologies, i.e. the Internet, the global information network, the President's Virtual Reception, "Electronic Parliament", "Digital Government" ("Electronic Government"), official electronic sites of state authorities and administrative bodies, video conference rooms, "hotlines", fast It is an effective result of cooperation between the state power and management, economic management bodies, authorities of all levels and citizens, which allows solving the most urgent problems of the population during the short period of operation of technologies such as communication phones.

On the one hand, this is a sign of the increasing confidence of our people in the state power and the rule of law, and on the other hand, the modern information and communication technologies are being effectively implemented in our society, the level of our people's use of them is increasing, and people use the opportunities and conveniences created in their daily life correctly and purposefully. showing that he can use it.

In short, the specific aspects of ensuring the right to appeal through digital technologies are that, firstly, it provides the opportunity to use the right to appeal from home, study, work or anywhere; secondly, it ensures getting a response about the results of the appeal in a short period of time; thirdly, it prevents wandering and wasting time; fourthly, money is saved materially; fifth, it prevents corruption;

¹⁰Ўзбекистон Республикаси қонун ҳужжатлари тўплами, 2017 й., 37-сон, 977-модда.

sixth, ensures open and transparent activities of state bodies; seventh, it puts an end to red tape in the competent bodies that consider appeals; Eighth, it increases citizens' confidence in the state.

In short, the introduction of the institute of appeals in digital technologies is provided for in Article 43 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan "The state ensures the rights and freedoms of citizens enshrined in the Constitution and laws"¹¹, is a confirmation that the legal norm is being fulfilled in the real sense.

¹¹Ўзбекистон Республикасининг Конституцияси. –Тошкент: «Ўзбекистон», 2018.

